

WATERSHED ANALYSIS- DELINEATION, MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS & LAND USE/LAND COVER MAPPING OF WATERSHED BY USING REMOTE SENSING & GIS TECHNIQUE

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Abstract

Study's methodology entails delineate the watershed boundary, contour, and drainage network in a GIS environment to generate morphometric characteristics with the help of DEM and Satellite imageries. Watershed's geomorphic properties have typical spatial dimensions, which is Remote Sensing and GIS come in as a useful tool. GIS facilitates the integration of maps and data. Most of the Sambar watershed is consist of the gentle slope 2-5 % and nearly level 0-2 %. According to the gentle slope area characteristics this is more suitable for constructing water conservation structures and cultivation and the nearly level surface is useful for storing the water for irrigation purpose. The total stream length is 139.5 km, which is the direct outcome of drainage development in a particular watershed. The basin contains total 188 number of streams. Ambar watershed has drainage density of 1.45 Km/Km² indicating coarse drainage texture due to highly resistant sub-soil material. The stream frequency is 1.93 streams/km² exhibits the positive correlation with the drainage density.

Keywords: Watershed, GIS, Remote sensing, Drainage.

Introduction

Watershed is an important term for soil and water conservation. Watershed management is the process of developing and implanting strategies wise project support programmes, and improvement of human communities. The main purpose of an integrated water development plan is to prevent water damage and to reduce water and soil erosion. Remote Sensing and Geographical Information system (GIS) is a technique commonly used for assessing the morphometric parameters, preparing the land use/land cover map and to generate the

various thematic maps of the watersheds. The study area of Sambar watershed is located in the Godavari - Purna (GP-56) basin in Parbhani District. The watershed is lies between 19°35'78.78" N and 76°87'88.44" E in the Parbhani district of Marathwada region in Maharashtra. The elevation/altitude is 414 meters above the sea level. The average annual rainfall is 650 mm and temperature in a summer season goes up to 42°C and 11°C in winter season. The climate of the district is Semi-arid, Humid & Sub-tropical

Materials And Methods

Materials used

Topo sheets: The Survey of India Topo sheet (SOI) No. 56A/15 on 1:50,000 scale was procured from the Survey of India from Nakshe Portal Website. Software: Upgraded QGIS & Google Earth Pro were used for preparing the

drainage networks and generating land use land cover map

Satellite Data

Digital Elevation Model (DEM) at 30-meter resolution, which is downloaded from Bhuvan.org website for morphometric analysis of

Sambar watershed. Landsat 8 satellite Imageries used for land use/land cover mapping. This is downloaded from USGS website.

Table a: Detail of satellite data used for morphometric analysis.

Sr. No.	Type of data	Detail	Sources	Software Use
1	SOI Toposheet	Toposheet No. E43E15 (56A/15) Scale: 1:50,000	Survey of India, Nakshe Portal	QGIS (Creating and using maps, Compiling Geographic Data, Analysing Map Information and Managing Geographical Information in Database)
2	DEM (Digital Elevation Model)	Resolution- 1-ARC 30 m resolution	SRTM (SRTM 1 Arc-Second Global) From USGS (United States of Geological Survey)	
3	GPS (Global Positioning System)	To Provide a geolocation and time information to GPS receiver.	Google	Google Earth

Table b: Detail of Land Use /Land Cover Image

Sr. No.	Types of data	Detail	Sources	Software use
1	Landsat 8 Imageries	Landsat Collection 1 Level -1 Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS C1	USGS (United States Geological Survey)	QGIS software (Image processing and preparation of land use/land cover map and calculate the area under the various feature.)
2	Google Earth Images	Ground Truthing and Validation	Google	Google Earth

Method used**Morphometric Analysis of Watershed by Using QGIS Software:**

Morphometric analysis is the very appropriate method for identifying the geographical and topological conditions of the watershed.

Delineation of Watershed:

Digital Elevation Model and Topo sheets used for the delineating the watershed boundary with the help of QGIS software.

Steps delineating the watershed boundaries in QGIS software is given below.

Calculation of Morphometric Parameters of Watershed

Remote Sensing and Geographical Information system based morphological analysis for the drainage and terrain analysis is very scientific and advanced tool for gathering the information about the watershed. The morphometric analysis of the Sambar watershed is carried out by calculation of Linear, Aerial and Relief parameters with the help of QGIS software.

Results And Discussion

Preparation of Various Thematic Maps: The various thematic maps such as base map, slope map, contour map, hill shade map, drainage map is prepared with the help of topo sheet and digital elevation model in QGIS software.

Digital Elevation model: DEM represent the highest and lowest elevation of the watershed in meters. Highest elevation 419 m and lowest elevation 370 m has been found for Sambar watershed which is shown in figure

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Table c: Detail of Linear, Areal and Relief parameters

Sr. No.	Morphometric Aspects	Parameters
1	Linear Aspect	i. Stream order ii. Stream Number iii. Stream Length iv. Bifurcation Ratio
2	Areal Aspect	i. Area ii. Perimeter iii. Length of watershed iv. Drainage Density v. Stream Frequency vi. Elongation Ratio vii. Circulatory Ratio viii. Form Factor ix. Length of Overland Flow x. Compactness Coefficient xi. Constant Channel Maintenance
3	Relief Aspect	i. Watershed Relief ii. Relative Relief iii. Relief Ratio iv. Relative Relief ratio v. Ruggedness Number

Slope Map

Table 1: Area in ha. Under the different percent slope classes

Sr. No.	Slope Classes (%)	Area (ha)	Area (%)
1	0-1	1600.23	16.49
2	1-2	3475.55	35.81
3	2-5	4376.71	45.10
4	5-9	233.9	2.41
5	9-16	17.18	0.18
Total		9703.57	100

Fig: Slope Map of Sambar Watershed

Aspect Map

Table 2: Area under the different aspects

Sr. No.	Degree	Area (ha)	Percentage (%)
1	North-1 (0°-22.5°)	1255.23	13
2	North-East (22.5 °--67.5 °)	1156.37	12
3	East (67.5-112.5)	1148.53	12
4	South-East (112.5-157.5)	1095.49	11
5	South (157.5-202.5)	1085.23	11
6	South-West (202.5-247.5)	880.45	9
7	West (247.5-292.5)	1091.12	11
8	North-West (292.5-337.5)	1170.23	12
9	North-2 (337.5-360)	819.26	9
Total		9701.91	100

Fig: Aspect Map of the Sambar watershed

Contour Map:

The contour map describes the elevation characteristics of the watershed area. Digital Elevation Model (DEM) was use generate the contour lines in the studyarea.From the figure it was illustrated by the elevation of the contours was ranges from 366 – 414 m from the mean sea level

Morphometric Analysis of Sambar watershed

Table 3: Linear Parameters of the Sambar watershed

Stream Orders (U)	Stream No. (N _u)	Stream Length (L _u) (Km)	Mean Stream Length (L _{sm}) (Km)	Stream Length Ratio (S _{RL})	Bifurcation Ratio (R _b)
1 st Order	97	71.64	0.738	-	-
2 nd Order	54	39.96	0.740	0.55	1.79
3 rd Order	19	14.625	0.769	0.36	2.84
4 th Order	15	11.50	0.766	0.78	1.26
5 th Order	1	1.79	0.597	0.15	15
Total	186	139.5	Average = 0.722	Average = 0.46	Average = 5.22

Table 4: Areal Aspects of the Sambar watershed

Sr. No.	Areal parameters	Units	Value
1	Area (A)	Km ²	97.01
2	Perimeter (P)	Km	70
3	Length of watershed (L _b)	Km	17.63
4	Drainage Density (D _d)	Km/Km ²	1.45
5	Drainage Texture (D _t)	Km ⁻¹	2.7
6	Stream Frequency (F _s)	Km ⁻²	1.93
7	Elongation Ratio (R _e)	-	0.630
8	Circulatory Ratio (R _c)	-	0.25
9	Length of overland flow (L _o)	Km	0.34
10	Form Factor (R _f)	-	0.31
11	Constant Channel Maintenance (C _{cm})	-	0.68
12	Compactness Coefficient (C _c)	-	2.00

Relief Aspect:

Table 5: Relief Parameters of the Sambar Watershed

Sr. No.	Relief Parameters	Units		Values	
1	Maximum Elevation (R)	Meter	Km	419	0.419
2	Minimum Elevation (r)	Meter	Km	370	0.370
3	Relative Relief (H)	Meter	Km	49	0.049
4	Relief Ratio (R_r)	-		0.0026	
5	Relative Relief Ratio (H_r)	%		0.07	
6	Ruggedness Number (R_n)	-		0.074	

Table 6: Land Use/Land Cover Mapping of Sambar Watershed

Sr. No.	Name	Area (Ha)	Percentage (%)
1	Agricultural land	4135	43%
2	Barren land	3392	35%
3	Waterbodies	630	6%
4	Fallow land	650	7%
5	Forest area	502	5%
6	Urban area	390	4%
Total		9699	100